

Teacher Education for Developing Teaching Competency: A Study of Two-Year B.Ed. Programme of Gauhati University

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Abstract:

The two year B.Ed. program found it's functioning all over India in the year 2015. The objective is to develop more professionalism among future teachers, to meet the gap between theory and practice of teaching with their continued engagement in schools, and to establish close relations between different curricular areas. But how far the two year B.Ed. curriculum is able to develop the expected teaching competency among the student teacher is a big question. In order to answer the question in the present paper an attempt was made to find out the opinion of student teachers in developing teaching competency among Student Teachers through two-year B.Ed. programme of Gauhati University, Guwahati through an empirical investigation of 100 student teachers enrolled in B.Ed. Programme under Gauhati University. The researcher used one self constructed standardized scales to do so and the results are being incorporated.

Keywords: Two-Year B.Ed. Programme, Teaching Competency

1. Introduction:

The NCF-2005 states that teacher education programmes today train teachers to adjust to a system in which education is seen as the transmission of information. Efforts at curricular reform have not been adequately supported by teacher education. Existing teacher education programmes neither accommodate the emerging ideas in context and pedagogy nor address the issue of linkages between society and school. There is a little space for engagement with innovative educational experiments; it is in the practice of teacher education indicates that knowledge is treated as given, embedded in the curriculum and accepted without question. Curriculum, syllabi and textbooks are hardly critically examined by the trainee teacher or the regular teacher. Language ability of the teacher needs to be improved, as the existing teacher education programmes hardly recognise the centrality of language in the curriculum. It is assumed that link subjects are automatically formed during the programme. Generally teacher education programmes provide little scope for student teachers to reflect on their experience and thus fail to empower teachers as agents of change. Education reforms invariably accord highest concern to improve teacher effectiveness. It requires consistent up gradation of teacher education programme. Over the last 2 decades in India, the issue of curriculum renewal and extended duration of secondary stage teacher education has received serious consideration. Recommendations of various commissions and committees indicate the preference for longer duration of B.Ed. programme. It was also endorsed by the Hon'ble Supreme Court of India in its judgment on 15th June 1993. The Teachers Education Institutes are meant to teach children of impressionable age and we cannot let loose on the innocent and unwary children the teachers who haven't received proper and adequate training. True, they will be required to pass the examination but that may not be sufficient. Training for a certain minimum period in a properly organized training institute is essential before a teacher may be duly launched. The NCTE prepared the curriculum framework for teacher education in the year 1998 and for the first time made the recommendation for beginning a two-year B.Ed. programme to prepare quality teachers. The NCERT in cooperation with NCTE developed four different syllabus for initiating this two-year B.Ed. programmed in its four regional institutions in the year 1999. The experience of running these programmes for over 9 years

proved to be valuable indicators for the present exercise of preparing effective teachers who could cope with the emerging challenges in their professions. Accordingly, the two-year B.Ed. programme aims at a total development of the student teacher; mainly in skills and knowledge, in individual care of the learner and also in methods and evaluation designed to facilitate learning. It aims at developing understanding of and competence to render disciplinary knowledge into forms relevant to stage specific understanding of teaching learning condition apprehended through intensive study of conceptual explanations, observation and analysis of live classroom conditions as well as hand on experiences and longer duration of field experience.

2. The rationale of the study:

Competence in teaching requires performance skills as well as knowledge and higher-level conceptualizations. At a professional level, competency includes understanding the processes involved as well as having performance skills and an academic and theoretical background. Teaching competency is the skill, ability and capabilities possessed by the teacher so as to make the teaching-learning environment effective and productive thereby realising the full potential of teacher, students and in turn achieving the aims of education. According to Wilson (1973), "Teaching competency is said to be the knowledge, attitude, skills and self-perception as the products that derive from the mixture of these behaviours resulting in consistent pattern of behaviour leading to the attainment of predicted outcomes". According to Umarani (2001), "Teaching competency means an ability of a teacher to facilitate behavioural changes in learning. To be precise, teaching competencies are functional abilities of teachers to prove their teaching efficiency. Thus teaching competency would mean effective performance of all observable teacher behaviour that brings about desired outcome among pupil". Teaching competency identifies a single level of proficiency or a range of levels determined through theoretical or empirical process at which a teacher must perform. Competencies and performance are therefore inversely related. The major components of teaching competence are- Knowledge of subject matter, Communication skills, Curriculum planning and classroom instruction, Evaluation of student, Professional characteristics, Classroom management, Personal qualities, and Community relationships. This paper aims to find out how far this two-year B.Ed. programme of Gauhati University is able to develop the

teaching competency among Student Teachers. Being very thoughtful of the above significance, the investigator prepared their mind to carry out the study.

3. Statement of the Study:

“Teacher Education for Developing Teaching Competency: A Study of Two-Year B.Ed. Programme of Gauhati University”

4. Objectives of the Study:

- (i) To find out the opinion of Student Teachers in developing teaching competency through two-year B.Ed. programme.

5. Research Questions:

- (i) What are the opinions of Student Teachers in developing teaching competency through two-year B.Ed. programme?

6. Methodology:

Design of The study: The present study falls under the domain of qualitative research. The researcher used an exploratory descriptive survey method in this study.

Sampling: The research was conducted for the B.Ed. Student-Teachers (2nd Year only) of Private and Govt. Colleges which are affiliated to Gauhati University, Guwahati. In this study, the researcher took randomly 100 Student-Teachers (20 from each colleges) belongs to five (three Private and two Govt.) B.Ed. Colleges affiliated to Gauhati University, Guwahati, Assam.

Table-I (Distribution of the Sample)

Sl. No.	Category	Male	Female	Private College	Govt. College	Total
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1	Student-Teachers	40	60	65	35	100
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Figure-I (Distribution of the Sample)

Tool: The tool i.e. ‘Teaching Competency Scale’ was prepared and standardized by the researcher himself. The tool has been standardized by establishing reliability. The Cronbach’s coefficient alpha (α) was computed and the coefficient alpha (α) was found to be .94. Thus, the reliability of the Teaching Competency Scale has been established.

Data Analysis: The researcher used descriptive statistics, simple percentage, and histogram for analysis of data.

7. Result and findings:

In order to answer the research question i.e. what are the opinions of Student Teachers in developing teaching competency through two-year B.Ed. programme? The researcher used the ‘Teaching Competency Scale’ on Student Teachers of B.Ed. Colleges under Gauhati University. There are 64 statements under eight components in this scale i.e., (i) Subject Competency (ii) Communication (iii) Instructional Strategies (iv) Use of learning materials

(v) Class Management (vi) Evaluation (vii) Motivation (viii) Classroom Dynamics. These components are related to various aspects of teaching competency. Each statement contains five alternative responses for the Student Teacher, i.e. (a) Strongly Agree, (b) Agree, (c) Undecided, (d) Disagree and (e) Strongly Disagree.

Component wise table is formed and analysed on the basis of responses given by Student Teacher. Accordingly following results are found:

Table-II (Responses of Student Teachers):

(Showing item wise no (N) and percentage (%) of Student Teachers opted a, b, c, d & e options in support of the question asked under each components)

Response -	a		b		c		d		e	
Components	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
i	15	15%	21	21%	18	18%	29	29%	17	17%
ii	20	20%	35	35%	20	20%	15	15%	10	10%
iii	17	17%	33	33%	12	12%	18	18%	20	20%
iv	32	32%	38	38%	15	15%	10	10%	5	5%
v	22	22%	41	41%	22	22%	12	12%	3	3%
vi	27	27%	32	32%	21	21%	14	14%	6	6%
vii	14	14%	46	46%	15	15%	17	17%	8	8%
viii	29	29%	35	35%	11	11%	10	10%	15	15%
Average	176	22%	281	35.13%	134	16.75%	125	15.63%	84	10.5%

Figure-II (Component wise comparison for responses of Student Teachers in %)

In the Table-I and Figure-II (Student Teachers responses) clearly shows the following results:

Component (i) i.e. *Subject Competency*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 15% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Subject Competency among the student Teachers; where as 21% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 18% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 29% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 17% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (ii) i.e. *Communication*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 20% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Communication among the student Teachers; where as 35% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 20% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 15% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 10% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (iii) i.e. *Instructional Strategies*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 17% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati

University is able to develop the Competency in Instructional Strategies among the student Teachers; where as 33% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 12% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 18% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 20% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (iv) i.e. *Use of learning materials*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 32% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Use of learning materials among the student Teachers; where as 38% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 15% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 10% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 5% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (v) i.e. *Class Management*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 22% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Class Management among the student Teachers; where as 41% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 22% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 12% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 3% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (vi) i.e. *Evaluation*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 27% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Evaluation among the student Teachers; where as 32% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 21% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 14% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 6% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (vii) i.e. *Motivation*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 14% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Motivation among the student Teachers; where as 46% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 15% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 17% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 8% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Component (viii) i.e. *Classroom Dynamics*, shows that out of total 100 respondents 29% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in Classroom Dynamics among the student Teachers; where as 35% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 11% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 10% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 15% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

Moreover, if we see the average responses of all Components together, it shows that out of total 100 respondents 22% Student Teachers are Strongly Agreeing that Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum of Gauhati University is able to develop the Competency in the areas-(i) Subject Competency (ii) Communication (iii) Instructional Strategies (iv) Use of learning materials (v) Class Management (vi) Evaluation (vii) Motivation (viii) Classroom Dynamics among the student Teachers; where as 35.13% Student Teachers responded as Agree; 16.74% Student Teachers responded as Undecided; 15.63% Student Teachers responded as Disagree and 10.5% Student Teachers responded as Strongly Disagree.

8. Conclusion:

It is quite clear from the above result and findings that, majority of the Student Teachers have agreed that the two-year B.Ed. programme of Gauhati University is able to develop the teaching competency in the said Components i.e., (ii) Communication (iii) Instructional Strategies (iv) Use of learning materials (v) Class Management (vi) Evaluation (vii) Motivation (viii) Classroom Dynamics. But in case of component (i) i.e. Subject Competency, majority of Student Teachers are Disagreeing that the Two-Year B.Ed. programme of Gauhati University is able to develop this competency among Student Teachers.

However, a large part of Student Teachers have different opinions in regard to the statement that the two-year B.Ed. programme is able to develop the teaching competency among Student Teachers.

9. Recommendations:

Though Gauhati University brought out changes in the Two-Year B.Ed. Curriculum w.e.f. 2015-16 in the light of the new norms and standards of NCTE, 2014, which could develop

certain important competencies among the Student Teachers. But, significant content has not been added to the Curriculum of Two-Year B.Ed. Programme which can develop the Subject Competency among the Student Teachers. Therefore, there is an urgent need to modify the curriculum to fulfil the requirement.

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